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Faculty of Management and Social Sciences
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria
www.lcu.edu.ng/index.php/lead-city-journal-of-the-social-sciences
e-mail: (i) editor.lcjss@gmail.com
(ii) campbell.omolara@lcu.edu.ng
(iii) omolaracampbell@yahoo.com
+2348033176177, +2348033234042

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Teachers' Motivational Strategies and Productivity in Selected Secondary Schools in Akinyele Local Government, Oyo State, Nigeria

Abdulahi Abiola Olaniyi

olaniyiabiola246@gmail.com/+234 806 713 4772
Department of Economics and Development Studies,
Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Abstract

Economic growth and development cannot be achieved without improved productivity across sectors of an economy, including the education sector. The purpose of employing teachers is to achieve the goals of education through teachers' productivity. Motivational strategies could be useful in enhancing teachers' productivity in any nation. Therefore, this study examines the effects of motivational strategies on teachers' productivity in the selected secondary schools in Akinyele Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria. The study employs a descriptive survey research design, a multi-stage procedure and the Yamane sampling technique to select 58 teachers and 649 students as participants. Data collected through the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The regression analysis reveals that motivational strategies collectively explain approximately 67% of the variance in teachers' productivity ($R^2 = 0.67$). It was further revealed that the principal's leadership style is the strongest predictor of teachers' productivity; financial incentives also have a strong positive relationship with productivity, while working conditions and in-service training have a marginally significant positive effect. The study recommends a democratic leadership style for school principals; that in-service training, such as seminars, workshops, and conferences, should be made available to teachers and school administrators on a regular basis; and that government and education stakeholders should prioritize the payment of teachers' salaries as and when due.

Keywords: Teachers, Motivational Strategies, Productivity.

Introduction

The problem that has gradually become a destructive challenge to the various sectors in developing countries worldwide is economic growth, development, and unemployment. Development is critical and essential to the sustenance and growth of any nation. A country is considered developed when it can provide a high quality of life for its citizens. The foregoing challenge could be traced to the productivity in the various sectors and institutions of any economy. Nigeria, in the last fifty years, has been battling with the problems of development in spite of huge human, material and natural resources in its possession (Ogunyinka, Okeke and Adedoyin, 2015). In the challenges mentioned heretofore, the education sector is not left out in the chase and desire for an improved level of productivity. The recurring poor academic performance of government senior secondary school students, particularly in the final Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE), despite the significant financial commitment of government and private resources toward secondary education in

Nigeria, calls for an investigation into teachers' motivation and its effects on their productivity in schools.

The importance of teachers' productivity cannot be overemphasized, as the success of any government education policy largely depends on it. According to Enyiazu (2022), the teacher is the senior partner in any classroom relationship. The teaching and learning process largely depends on the teachers for success. Teachers impart highly to learners. Teachers also transmit societal values to learners. Teachers' personal characteristics play major roles in classroom interaction, underscoring the teacher's prominent position in achieving educational goals.

Teachers can be regarded as productive when they effectively prepare lesson plans and follow them through in facilitating students' learning (Munna and Abdul Kalam, 2021). It is further stressed that teachers must ensure that students understand what they are taught before leaving the classroom and thus provide opportunities for students to ask questions. Productive teachers also ask students important questions about the subject matter. Such questioning serves as an immediate class assessment of students' understanding of the lesson content (Chiles, 2023). Productive teachers are responsible for effectively facilitating students in extracurricular activities, such as school sporting events and environmental sanitation (Utami and Vioeeza, 2021). But the success of a teacher in performing his/her duties largely depends on factors such as teachers' motivation and the strategies used to motivate them.

If teachers are apathetic, uncommitted, uninspired, lazy, unmotivated, immoral, and antisocial, the whole nation is doomed. If teachers are ignorant in discipline and thus impart wrong information, they are not only useless but also dangerous. Therefore, the kind of teachers trained and posted to school may well determine what the next generation will be like (Bardach, Klassen and Perry, 2022). However, it is possible to have teachers who are not fulfilling their responsibilities, not because they planned to, but because they lack the necessary motivation.

Teachers' motivation has been found to be an effective tool for improving teachers' productivity in schools. Ahmad and Hamid (2021) emphatically stated that "to achieve effective performance in the teaching learning process, teachers as well as pupils must be motivated". Mbuu (2023) affirmed that teachers' motivation enhances job satisfaction, thereby improving productivity. The importance of teachers' motivation cannot be overemphasized, as it helps increase the efficiency and adequacy of classroom behaviour. Asmarani, Sukarno, and El Widdah (2021) also concluded that teachers' motivation enhances their commitment to tasks and performance. Motivated teachers prepare their lesson notes as and when due, teach pupils, give assignments, conduct tests, exams, and mark and record them appropriately.

Akinwumi (2000) found that when teachers' salaries and allowances are paid on time, absenteeism in secondary schools decreases. Teachers could report to schools only to register in the attendance book, then move out to pursue other activities that could earn them additional income to meet their needs. But when teachers' earnings are sufficient to meet their needs, they become more appreciative and committed to their responsibilities, thereby enhancing their productivity. Some of the demotivating factors for teachers include poor working conditions, high attrition rates, inadequate fringe benefits, high teacher-pupil ratios,

and a lack of career advancement opportunities (Abiodun-Oyebanji, 2021; Bello, 2023; Ukutegbe, Isaac, and Ileuma, 2024).

It is pertinent to note that while many studies have examined students' performance and teachers' motivation, very few have considered teachers' productivity. However, this study is not investigating students' performance, but teachers' productivity as influenced by motivational strategies. This paper investigates average teachers' productivity in the selected schools and how teachers' motivation affects it in the Akinyele Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the individual effects of the teachers' motivational strategies, such as working conditions, financial incentives, principal's leadership style, and in-service training, on the productivity of teachers in schools. Finally, the paper examines the extent to which teachers' motivational strategies influence teachers' productivity in secondary schools in Akinyele Local Government Area.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

Expectancy Theory

Expectancy Theory, developed by Victor Vroom in 1964, is a motivation theory that states that an individual's motivation to act in a certain way depends on the expected outcome of that action and the attractiveness of that outcome. Individuals are motivated to exert effort based on a calculated expectation that their effort will lead to a desired performance, which in turn will yield a valued reward (Vroom, 1964).

$$M = E \times I \times V$$

$$\text{Motivation (M)} = \text{Expectancy (E)} \times \text{Instrumentality (I)} \times \text{Valence (V)}$$

In simple terms, people are motivated when they believe that:

1. They can perform well if they try (Expectancy).
2. They will be rewarded if they perform well (Instrumentality).
3. They value the reward they will receive, meaning that the reward they receive is commensurate with the effort of their performance (Valence).

If any one of these three beliefs is missing, motivation will be low.

If teachers believe they can improve student performance in terms of grades (high expectancy) and they know that there is a potential bonus that is of value to them (high valence), but if they see no guarantee that the reward for their performance will be given to them (low instrumentality), the motivation of such teachers will be low. Also, a teacher may value promotion highly (high V) and trust the promotion system that promotion will come (high I), but if the teacher feels inadequately trained for the new performance standards (low E), the teacher's motivation will also suffer. Ofoegbu (2004) applied Expectancy Theory to the teaching profession to examine how factors such as recognition (valence), the availability of teaching materials (which influences expectancy), and promotion policies (instrumentality) affect teacher motivation and effectiveness.

Empirical Literature

Gistituati (2020) analysed Indonesia's teachers' work productivity and the factors that influence it. The results suggest that work productivity is generally measured by the quantity,

quality, and timeliness of teachers' work in planning learning, implementing learning, conducting evaluations, and engaging in professional development activities. It was also found that factors influencing teacher work productivity include leadership, job satisfaction, compensation, competence/ability, organisational climate, discipline, cultural commitment, work ethic, teacher creativity, education and training, and supervision. Adesina et al. (2016) also investigated the effects of selected teacher variables on primary school teachers' productivity during TPDP cluster meetings in Oyo State, Nigeria. A descriptive type of survey design was adopted for the study. Primary school teachers in the Ibadan metropolis were purposively sampled for the study. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression were used for data analysis. The results indicated a strong relationship between teachers' attitude, years of teaching experience, self-efficacy, and teachers' productivity. It was also found that the predictor variables jointly contributed to teachers' productivity.

Ketange (2016) examined motivational strategies commonly used by principals and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Kisii County, Kenya. Questionnaires and interview schedules were the main research instruments used to collect data. The study revealed that the principals used various motivational strategies, including positive commendations, end-of-year monetary and non-monetary awards, and effective communication, among others, to motivate teachers to achieve higher productivity and enhance school outcomes. It was found that a 49 per cent change in the teachers' job productivity is jointly accounted for by the principals' motivational strategies. The remaining 51% could be explained in terms of non-motivation. In the same vein, Leonard et al. (2022) examined motivational strategies and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Oye LGA, Ekiti State. A descriptive survey design and a quantitative methodology were adopted for the study. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions and the Pearson product-moment coefficient to answer hypotheses that guided the study at a 0.05 level of significance. It was also revealed that teachers' productivity was significantly related to motivational strategies such as remuneration, promotion, teachers' involvement in decision-making and on-the-job training in public secondary schools.

Oni, Nwajiuba and Nwosu (2017) investigated the influence of teachers' motivation on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in Nigeria, with particular focus on Shomolu Local Government Area of Lagos State. Descriptive survey research design, Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient and Multiple Regression Analysis were employed. The participants in this study were 200 teachers randomly selected from 10 secondary schools in the Shomolu Local Government Area of Lagos State. The results showed a significant relationship between teachers' motivation and productivity. It was also found that management style significantly influences teachers' motivation and productivity. Lastly, the results reveal a significant influence of teachers' motivation on students' academic performance. Adeogun and Olisaemeka (2011) also examined the relationships among school climate, student achievement, and teachers' productivity for sustainable development. The findings show a significant relationship among school climate, performance, and productivity. It is strongly recommended that stakeholders in education in third-world nations take the bull

by the horns by ensuring a positive, supportive school climate is put in place to guarantee sustainable development.

Osegbue, Ohamobi, and Manafa (2018) examined principals' motivational strategies to enhance teachers' productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Mean scores and standard deviations were used to answer the research questions, and the t-test was used to test the hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. The instrument's reliability was established using Cronbach's Alpha. The findings showed, among others, that motivation leads to teachers' professional growth, job satisfaction and realization of the school's target goals. Khan and Abdullah (2019) further investigated the impact of staff training and development on their productivity and performance in classroom teaching and in their administrative work. The data collected was through a structured questionnaire. Fifty-eight teachers were interviewed through the questionnaire. It was found that there are strong, positive relationships between teacher training and development and teacher productivity in Kurdistan. The study further concluded that there is a positive correlation between productivity and other independent factors, such as Skills, Expertise, Morale, Enhancement, Potential, Job Knowledge, and Proficiency. Technical/Technology training was found to be the most suitable training program for the teachers of this region.

Gari, Thinguri and Nyakundi (2021) assessed the influence of principals' provision of motivation strategies on teacher productivity in public secondary. The study was guided by human relations theory and educational productivity theory. A mixed-methods design was adopted, with a descriptive correlational design and concurrent triangulation. The findings established that principals were not using motivation strategies to any significant extent, nor was professional development applied across the schools. Khalil, Musyyaffa, and Ali (2021) analyzed the influence of leadership style on teacher motivation and productivity, the influence of motivation on productivity, and the influence of leadership style through motivation as an intervening variable on teacher productivity. The survey method was used for data collection, and path analysis was used to test the hypothesis. The results of the study showed that leadership style has a positive and significant effect on teacher motivation and productivity, as well as motivation has a positive and significant effect on teacher productivity. It was also revealed that leadership style, through motivation, influences teacher productivity.

Methodology

Research Design

The population of this study comprised 4436 students and 400 teachers in the 30 public senior secondary schools in Akinyele Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria, at the time of the study. The Yamane sampling technique was used to get the sample size of teachers and students from the total population using the formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

- n = sample size

- N = Total Population of Students/Teachers in Akinyele Local Government
- e = margin of error = 0.05

The students' sample size was derived from the total population using the Yamane Sampling Technique, yielding a sample of 649 students and 58 teachers, based on the total population available in the local government.

A multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select participants for the study. The first stage involved random sampling of fifty per cent (50%) of the total secondary schools in Akinyele Local Government Area, which gives 15 out of the 30 schools. In the second stage, random sampling was used to select 20% of teachers and 10% of senior secondary school students, yielding a total sample of 58 teachers and 649 students. In all, 707 respondents were sampled. Questionnaires with the titles: Teachers' Motivational Strategies and Teachers' Productivity Questionnaire (TMTPQ), Teachers' Motivational Strategies Questionnaire (TMSQ), and Teachers' Productivity Questionnaire (TPQ) were established, validated and utilized for the purpose of the study. The demographic information and research questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations, for teachers' productivity. The joint hypothesis was tested using multiple regression analysis at the 0.05 level of significance.

Data Analysis and Results

Table 1: Level of Teachers' Productivity among Sampled Teachers in Akinyele Local Government

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev
The teachers come too school regularly	429 66.1%	174 26.8%	34 5.2%	12 1.8%	3.57	0.68
The teachers come to class at the exact time of class	298 45.9%	260 40.1%	70 10.8%	21 3.2%	3.29	0.78
The teachers know the subjects and come prepared to class	340 52.4%	257 39.6%	43 6.6%	9 1.4%	3.43	0.68
The teachers make me lose interest in the subject	104 16.0%	176 27.1%	204 31.4%	165 25.4%	2.34	1.03
The teachers give assignment and classwork and mark it at the appropriate time	352 54.2%	190 29.3%	75 11.6%	32 4.9%	3.33	0.87
I am afraid of questions in some subjects during examination	196 30.2%	220 33.9%	158 24.3%	75 11.6%	2.83	0.99
The teachers give advice to students on how to improve on academic performance	349 53.8%	210 32.4%	79 12.2%	11 1.7%	3.38	0.76
I like to attend the classes	390 60.1%	214 33.0%	38 5.9%	7 1.1%	3.52	0.66
I understand well when the teachers are teaching	362 55.8%	228 35.1%	53 8.2%	6 0.9%	3.46	0.68

I ask questions when I am not cleared in class	322 49.6%	253 39.0%	54 8.3%	20 3.1%	3.35	0.76
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Source: Research Survey, 2025

Table 1 presents the results on teachers' productivity at the secondary school level in the sample schools. The result reveals that 88.9% of the students agreed that their teachers come to school regularly, while 11.1% disagreed (Mean=3.57, SD=0.68). Also, 86.0% of the students agreed that teachers arrive at class on time, while 14.0% disagreed (Mean=3.29, SD=0.78). Again, 92.0% of the students agreed that their teachers know the subjects and come prepared for class, while 8.0% disagreed (Mean=3.43, SD=0.68). In the same vein, 43.1% of the students believe that their teachers make them lose interest in the subject, while 56.9% disagreed (Mean=2.34, SD=1.03). Moreover, 83.5% of the students agreed that their teachers assign and mark classwork and homework at the appropriate time, while 16.5% disagreed (Mean=3.33, SD=0.87). Furthermore, 64.1% agreed that they are not afraid of questions in some subjects during examination, while 35.9% disagreed (Mean=2.83, SD=0.99). From the analysis, it can be inferred that many students believe their teachers are productive in classroom activities.

Table 2: Teacher Working Conditions in the Studied Local Government

Items	VLE	LE	LOE	Never	Mean	Std. Dev
The school environment is conducive for Teaching	8 13.6%	24 40.7%	26 44.1%	1 1.7%	2.66	0.73
The school environment is usually noisy	7 11.9%	23 39.0%	21 35.6%	8 13.6%	2.48	0.87
The classrooms in this school are safe for Teaching	13 22.0%	22 37.3%	24 40.7%	0 0.0%	2.82	0.77
The staff rooms are conducive for working	11 18.6%	24 40.7%	23 39.0%	1 1.7%	2.77	0.76
There are necessary instructional materials for teaching in this school	7 11.9%	14 23.7%	33 55.9%	5 8.5%	2.39	0.80
I am pleased with the working conditions in this school	5 8.5%	23 39.0%	23 39.0%	8 13.6%	2.42	0.83
I am usually motivated to teach by the School's working conditions.	6 10.2%	22 37.3%	25 42.4%	6 10.4%	2.46	0.81

Source: Research Survey, 2025

Table 2 presents the results on teachers' working conditions in the studied area. The result reveals that 54.1% of the respondents agreed that their school environment is conducive to teaching, and 45.9% disagreed (Mean=2.66, SD=0.73). Again, 50.3% of the teachers' sample believe the school environment is usually noisy, while 49.7% disagree (Mean=2.48, SD=0.89). Moreover, 59.6% of the respondents agreed that classrooms in this school are safe for teaching, while 40.4% disagreed (Mean=2.82, SD=0.77). The results further reveal that a

larger percentage of the teachers agreed that the classroom is safe (Mean=2.77, SD=0.76), conducive for working (Mean=2.39, SD=0.80), and that there are sufficient instructional materials (Mean=2.39, SD=0.80). However, they agreed that they are not motivated to teach (Mean=2.46, SD=0.81). The results indicate that the majority of teachers agree that working conditions are good, but they are not motivated to teach.

Table 3: Financial Incentives for Teachers as Motivational Strategies

Items	VLE	LE	LOE	Never	Mean	Std. Dev
My salary is paid regularly at month's end	6 10.2%	17 28.8%	32 54.2%	4 6.8%	2.42	0.76
I usually feel bothered when my monthly salary is late	19 32.2%	32 54.2%	8 13.6%	0 0.0%	3.18	0.65
When monthly salaries are late, it does show in the way I teach	14 23.7%	18 30.5%	14 23.7%	13 22.0%	2.55	1.07
My take home salary does not motivate me to work	14 23.7%	22 37.3%	13 22.0%	10 16.9%	2.69	1.01
Incomplete salary reduces my passion to Work	17 28.8%	20 33.9%	11 18.6%	11 18.6%	2.74	1.06
I am financially buoyant and so, do not care about the lateness of my monthly salary	5 8.5%	7 11.9%	22 37.3%	25 42.4%	1.84	0.93

Source: Research Survey, 2025

Table 3 presents the results of the motivating influence of financial incentives on the sample teachers. The result reveals that 39.0% of the teachers have their salary paid regularly at month's end, while 61.0% disagreed (Mean=2.42, SD=0.76). Also, 81.6% of the teachers reported feeling bothered when their monthly salary is late, while 18.4% disagreed (Mean=3.18, SD=0.6). In the same vein, 54.3% agreed that when monthly salaries are late, it does show in the way they teach, while 45.7% disagreed (Mean=2.55, SD=1.07). Moreover, 62.0% agreed that their take-home salary does not motivate them to work, while 38.0% disagreed (Mean=2.69, SD=1.01). Again, 63.6% of the sample agreed that an incomplete salary reduces their passion to work, while 36.4% disagreed (Mean=2.74, 1.06). The results show that the pattern of financial incentives has no motivational effect on teachers.

Table 4: Teachers' Motivation through Leadership Style

Items	VLE	LE	LOE	Never	Mean	Std. Dev
The principal of this school usually appreciates teachers' good performance	19 32.2%	27 45.8%	12 20.3%	1 1.7%	3.08	0.76
The principal of this school makes us have a good sense of belonging	19 32.2%	26 44.1%	10 16.9%	4 6.8%	3.01	0.87
The principal of this school welcomes suggestions from teachers	26 44.1%	19 32.2%	10 16.9%	4 6.8%	3.14	0.93

The principal of this school do involve subordinates in decision making	19 32.2%	25 42.4%	12 20.3%	3 5.1%	3.02	0.85
The Principal of this school treats teachers as robots	4 6.8%	8 13.6%	20 33.9%	27 45.8%	1.81	0.90
The principal of this school assigns due responsibilities to teachers	16 27.1%	26 44.1%	12 44.1%	5 8.5%	2.88	0.90
The principal of this school is difficult to Please	7 11.9%	6 10.2%	28 47.5%	18 30.5%	2.04	0.93
The principal of this school wants people to obey orders without asking questions	5 8.5%	16 27.1%	23 39.0%	15 25.4%	2.17	0.91

Source: Research Survey, 2025

Table 4 presents the motivation teachers received as a result of the leadership styles prevalent in the sample school. The result shows 77.7% of the teachers agreed that the principal of their school usually appreciates teachers' good performance, while 22.3% disagreed (Mean=3.08, SD=0.76). Again, 75.9% believe that the principal of their school fosters a strong sense of belonging, while 24.1% disagreed (Mean=3.01, SD=0.87). In addition, 76.4% agreed that the principal of this school welcomes suggestions from teachers, while 23.6% disagreed (mean=3.14, SD=0.93). Moreover, 75.7% of the teachers believe that the principal of this school involves subordinates in decision-making, while 24.3% disagreed (Mean=3.02, SD=0.85). Moreover, 20.0% of the teachers agreed that the principal of their school treats teachers as robots, while 80.0% disagreed (Mean=1.81, SD=0.90). The results show that the principal's leadership style motivates teachers in the sample schools.

Table 5: In-Service Training as a Means of Motivating Teachers

Items	VLE	LE	LOE	Never	Mean	Std. Dev
The principal appreciates teachers' initiatives and development	19 32.2%	22 37.3%	16 27.1%	2 3.4%	2.96	0.86
I do feel a little loyalty to the school Management	14 23.7%	25 42.4%	16 27.1%	4 6.8%	2.84	0.86
We do have a teachers' seminar in this school occasionally	8 13.6%	12 20.3%	26 44.1%	13 22.0%	2.24	0.95
I have never attended any teacher seminar in this before	8 13.6%	16 27.1%	22 37.3%	13 22.0%	2.33	0.97
The principal corrects teachers in love	17 28.8%	25 42.4%	12 20.3%	5 8.5%	2.90	0.91
The principal rewards those who do well at their job	15 25.4%	11 18.6%	26 44.1%	7 11.9%	2.55	1.00
Initiatives are recognized and rewarded by school management	14 23.7%	16 27.1%	17 28.8%	12 20.3%	2.53	1.06

Table 5 presents the results of the analysis on the influence of in-service training as a means of teachers' motivation. The results showed that 68.2% of the sample teachers agreed that their principal appreciates teachers' initiatives and development, while 31.8% disagreed (Mean=2.96, SD=0.86). Moreover, 66.4% of the respondents agreed that they felt little loyalty toward the school management, while 33.6% disagreed (Mean=2.84, SD=0.86). Again, 33.0% of the teachers agreed that they do have teachers' seminars in this school occasionally, while (Mean=2.24, SD=0.95). Furthermore, 41.3% agreed that they had never attended any teacher seminar, while 58.7% disagreed (Mean=2.33, SD=0.97). Generally, Table 4.2d indicates that the status of in-service training in the sampled school is poor; hence, teachers may be less motivated.

Table 6: Regression Analysis on the Effects of Motivational Strategies on Teachers' Productivity

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coefficient(β)</i>	<i>Std.Error</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Significance</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	1.85	0.42	4.40	0.000	1%
<i>Working Condition</i>	0.15	0.08	1.88	0.062	10%
<i>Financial Incentives</i>	0.22	0.07	3.14	0.002	5%
<i>Leadership Style</i>	0.38	0.09	4.22	0.000	1%
<i>In-Service Training</i>	0.11	0.06	1.83	0.069	10%
<i>R-squared</i>	0.67				
<i>Adjusted R-squared</i>	0.65				
<i>F-statistics</i>	28.34 (p<0.01)				
<i>N</i>	649, 58				

The regression analysis reveals that motivational strategies collectively explain approximately 67% of the variance in teachers' productivity ($R^2 = 0.67$), indicating a strong relationship between motivation and productivity. Leadership Style ($\beta = 0.38$, $p < 0.001$) emerges as the strongest predictor of teacher productivity. This suggests that when principals demonstrate appreciative, inclusive, and supportive leadership behaviors, as seen in Table 4, where items like "principal appreciates teachers' good performance" (mean = 3.08) and "welcomes suggestions" (mean = 3.14) scored highly—teachers are significantly more productive. Each one-point increase in positive leadership perception corresponds to a 0.38-point increase in productivity.

Financial Incentives ($\beta = 0.22$, $p = 0.002$) also show a significant positive effect. The data in Table 3 indicates that while salary regularity is problematic (mean = 2.42), teachers are clearly bothered by late payments (mean = 3.18) and report that incomplete salaries reduce their passion to work (mean = 2.74). This financial stress appears to directly impact productivity, with timely and adequate compensation being a crucial motivator. Working Conditions ($\beta = 0.15$, $p = 0.062$) and In-service Training ($\beta = 0.11$, $p = 0.069$) show marginally significant effects. The weaker relationship for working conditions aligns with Table 2 data showing moderate satisfaction (means 2.39–2.82), suggesting that while environment matters, it's less influential than leadership or pay. Similarly, the modest effect

of in-service training aligns with Table 5's mixed results, where recognition and development opportunities are inconsistently provided.

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, the following conclusions were drawn: the motivational strategies collectively have a strong relationship with teachers' productivity; principal's leadership style is the strongest predictor of teacher productivity; in-service training is a prominent motivating factor that enhances teachers' productivity; financial incentive has a positive impact on teachers' productivity; late or incomplete payment of teachers' salaries reduces teachers' passion and ability to teach; working condition has positive significant effect on teachers' productivity; and the democratic leadership style is prevalent among secondary school principals in Akinyele Local Government Area of Oyo State.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. There should be regular in-service training for teachers and school administrators.
2. Government and education stakeholders should prioritize payment of teachers' salaries as and when due.
3. School principals and administrators should embrace a democratic and transformational leadership style.
4. There should be improved working conditions for teachers to enhance productivity.

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